

AUTHENTIC MATERIAL IN WRITING

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Authentic materials are print or learner-contextualised materials and activities used in the classroom in ways that they would be used in the lives of learners outside their classes. [3; 5] Another book states that authentic materials are print materials used in ways that they would be used in the lives of learners outside of their adult education classes. So in this case we can define the authentic materials are spoken or written language data that has been produced in the course of genuine communication, and not specifically written for purposes of language teaching.

Authentic materials, when appropriately selected and implemented, can be used to develop tasks that depart from formulaic language learning and provide a bridge between the linguistic skill of learners and their professional knowledge goals. This successful also considered to the teacher how the teacher can implement the materials with the students' skill in the class. [1; 21] According to the definition of authentic materials, the use of authentic materials has a positive value that make students highly motivated. Because using authentic materials in the classroom is to make students not only learn in the 'safe' area and controlled language learning environment, but also to encounter the language use in the real word. So the students can learn the varying material and using the language in the real context not only in the classroom that make the materials just for language learning.

Authentic materials in language teaching are classified to use them as per the needs of a particular class. Authentic materials can be classified into three categories. First, authentic Listening- Viewing Materials like: TV commercials, quiz shows, cartoons, news clips, comedy shows, movies, soap operas, professionally audio-taped short stories and novels, radio ads, songs, documentaries, etc. Second, Authentic Visual Materials: Slides, photographs, paintings, children' artwork, stick- figure drawings, wordless street signs, silhouettes, pictures from magazine, ink blots, postcard pictures, etc. Third, authentic Text Materials: Newspaper articles, movie advertisements, lyrics to songs, restaurant menus, street signs, cereal boxes, etc. [3; 7]

The authentic materials are variety; it may spoken or written language data. It can be: Cartoons, Book Reviews, Feature articles, News, Reports, Letters, Editorial Comments, Recipes, Advertisements, Horoscopes, TV and Radio, programmes, Weather reports, News Reports, Sports, news, Problem Pages and many others. [1; 21]

Good writing in English requires good grammar and good organization. So, writing is not easy, it takes study and practice to develop this skill. In principle, to write means to try to produce or reproduce written messages. It is important to note that writing is a “process”, not a “product”. This means that a piece of writing, whether it is composition for your English class or a short story, is never complete, it is always possible to review and revise, and review and revise again. We also consider what we are writing; we should have something to convey.

The methodology involves selecting authentic materials based on criteria such as relevance, authenticity, and engagement, as well as implementing pre-writing activities, text analysis techniques, and writing tasks and exercises. [4; 171] There are four main stages in the writing process: prewriting, planning, writing and revising drafts and writing the final copy to hand in. According to Firth, he argues that language should be studied in actual, attested, authentic instances of use, not as intuitive, invented, isolated sentences. He further argues that ‘the placing of a text as a constituent in a context of situation contributes to the statement of meaning since situations are set up to recognize meaning. [2; 175] Similar views are echoed by Stubbs, where he argues that human intuition about language is highly specific not at all a good guide to what actually use language.

Authentic materials can be broadly classified in audio, visual, and printed materials. Audio materials involve those that learners can listen to. These can be grouped into three. First is television programming including commercials, quiz shows, interactive talk shows, cartoon, news, and forecast reports. The second group is radio programming including interviews, interactive talk shows, and radio advertisements. The third group involves taped conversations, including one-sided telephone conversations, meetings, short stories, poem and novels.

Functional writing text that may benefit from these authentic materials include advertisements, dialogues, news articles, weather forecast reports, interview schedules, agenda for meeting, minutes, short stories, plays, poem, and novels. It means that there are so many resources that can be taken for teaching materials by using authentic materials. [3; 7]

The authentic materials can be found easily since they are available in daily life. When selected and implemented appropriately as teaching materials and real example provider, authentic materials serve many advantages. Dealing with the students' improvement in choice of dictions, some factors in teaching learning process was also involved. Other aspect is collaboration of visual media and demonstration performed which were equipped by picture and realia. Those factors can help the students to be familiar with new vocabularies and make them easy to remember the new vocabularies. In addition, authentic materials facilitate students to guess the meaning of the dictions that the students do not know yet since the visual aids give meaning to the text. As the old saying said 'practice make better', writing practice in every meeting and teachers feedback on the students writing help students to write the vocabularies appropriately to their spelling. As stated by Harmer, teacher's feedback on students writing is one of the ways that can encourage students to write and correct their mistakes.

References:

1. Asif Masood, "Exploiting Authentic Materials for Developing Writing Skills at Secondary Level", *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, (Vol. 1, 2013), p. 21
2. Firth, J.R, *A Synopsis of Linguistic Theory*, (London: Longman, 1957), p. 175
3. Geoffrey M. Maroko, *the Authentic Materials Approach in the Teaching of Functional Writing in the Classroom*, (Reinelt, 2010), p. 5-7
4. Gulnara A., Bibisanem A. Methodology of developing writing skill through authentic materials //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 5-1. – С. 171-173.